

EXPLORING PSYCHOLOGICAL HELP SEEKING BEHAVIOR AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS: A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

University students often face a range of mental health challenges, yet many do not seek professional psychological help due to deeply rooted societal and cultural factors. The current qualitative study explores the psychological help seeking behaviour among university students. This study aiming to uncover the personal, social, and cultural factors that influence their decisions. For this purpose, sample of (N=14) were selected through convenient sampling and semi-structured interviews were conducted together in-depth information from participants. After data collection the interviews verbatim were transcribed and analyzed using reflective thematic analysis, resulting in the extraction of five major themes Mental Health Awareness, which highlighted students' varying levels of knowledge about mental health issues and services; Help-seeking behavior facilitators and barriers, which identified factors such as stigma, fear of judgment, and peer influence; Social and Cultural factors, emphasizing the impact of societal norms, family expectations, and religious beliefs on students decisions; personal coping strategies, where students discussed alternative methods for managing mental health issues, such as self-reliance and informal support from friends and family; and Recommendations for further improvement, where participants offered suggestions to make mental health services more accessible and culturally sensitive. The findings reveal the complexity of help-seeking behavior and underscore the importance of addressing cultural and societal barriers, improving mental health literacy, and creating a supportive university environment that encourages students to seek professional help. These insights provide a foundation for developing more effective, student-centered mental health programs and policies.

INTRODUCTION

Emerging adulthood is a unique transition period of student lives which coincides with the university education where they continue to strive for autonomy and sense of self while also dealing with issues brought on by their academic experience (Rickwood, Deane, Wilson, & Ciarrochi, 2005). Students at universities may have to cope with a variety of concerns that come

up. Mental health issues are a growing concern among university students because these settings can be extremely stressful due to social demands, academic demands, and financial difficulties. So, the current study investigates the attitudes, perceptions and experiences of student about psychological help seeking behaviour.

Moreover, this study also explores the cultural, social and religious factors that shape their help seeking behaviour for mental health.

The act of actively seeking assistance from others is referred to as "help-seeking" in most contexts. It involves talking to others in order to get understanding, counsel, knowledge, treatment, and all-around support in reaction to an issue or traumatic event. Since asking for help is a kind of coping that depends on other people, it frequently depends on social skills and connection with others (Rickwood, et.al., 2005).

According to Cornally and McCarthay (2011), The concept of "help-seeking" is used in opposition to, or in addition to, "health-seeking," and it is defined as a component of both disease behavior and wellness. According to their definition, seeking help is acting in a way that is intended to get professional aid for a mental or physical issue. People, especially students, seek assistance when they are experiencing personal problems, physical illness, or mental suffering.

Many people who are experiencing issues, crises, difficulties, uncertainties, disappointments, or worries seek assistance. Interactions with other people, with social contexts, with organizations, and with institutions can lead to problematic circumstances. According to Gerard (2007), these issues frequently result in emotional upheaval and lack definitive answers. The person who is having trouble with the issue typically lacks the resources necessary to handle it well. Even with life-threatening issues, asking for help can frequently enable the person to manage the situation more skillfully. Therefore, the purpose of psychological help is not to solve problems but rather to assist the distressed person in efficiently managing their problems or perhaps overcoming them by seizing new opportunities in life.

Many factors, including fear of therapy, managing emotions, sharing personal information, stigma, societal standards, gender, age, accessibility to facilities, and nature of the problem, have been considered as deterrents to getting psychological help (Vogel, Wester & Larson, 2007). Treatment-related anxieties may stem from an individual's expectation about the professional's approach to their care. Conversely, this expectation relates to a person's understanding of the possible risks associated with sharing personal information with another person

(Vogel & Wester, 2003). When someone asks for assistance, there's a chance they'll feel misinterpreted, scrutinized, or disregarded.

According to Rickwood et al. (2006), "help-seeking behavior is often moderated by various factors, which can either promote or act as a barrier." Of them, socio-cultural influences have been found to be among the most significant. The traditional belief system and cultural explanatory models of mental disease were reported to be particularly influential in the choice of where to seek health care, according to a Ugandan study on the behavior of persons seeking help for mental illnesses (Nserek et al., 2011).

Cultural differences in the barriers to getting psychological treatment have been extensively researched. The reason why people do not use psychological services as much as one would think has been suggested by the researchers on multiple occasions. Attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control all have an impact on intentions, which are crucial in determining and carrying out conduct (Ajzen, 2005). The best indicators of actually seeking psychological help are attitudes toward doing so. Individuals who are open to sharing personal information are more likely to turn to a professional psychological for help (Leech, 2007).

Literature review

According to the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (2013), at least thirty percent of Pakistan's population is comprised up of young adults (ages 15 to 29). It is a nation in many respects, one that is experiencing fast psychological development and a growing impact on traditional family dynamics, values, and societal institutions. In Pakistan, talking about mental health is still highly frowned upon. There is a societal norm that denies or minimizes the reality of mental health issues.

There is still stigma associated with mental health in Pakistan, and a lot of people are hesitant to go for treatment due to social norms, a lack of understanding and limited access to professional services. Research on the help-seeking behavior of university students is growing, despite its modest sample size. Studies have indicated that mental health issues are common among students, with notable instances of stress, anxiety, and depression being observed (Mirza & Jenkins, 2004). But the primary

barriers for seeking professional assistance continue to be stigma, ignorance, and restricted access to mental health services (Naeem et al., 2016).

Various factors influence students' decision to seek help and how they go about doing so, according to research on help-seeking behavior among university students worldwide. These include one's own beliefs on mental health, the stigma associated with it, awareness of the resources that are available, and the perceived efficacy of those resources. For example, a study carried out in the United States discovered that students' attitudes toward stigma and their prior experiences with mental health services had a major impact on their readiness to ask for treatment (Eisenberg, Hunt, & Speer, 2012).

Theoretical Framework

According to the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 2002), which contends that people are more likely to ask for help when they feel more knowledgeable about the process, notice changes in the social norms surrounding the issue (such as a decrease in the stigma associated with mental illness), get support from important people for their need, and believe they have the ability to ask for help a concept known as perceived behavioral control. We are able to investigate the complex aspects that shape university students' attitudes on seeking for help through the comprehensive use of this behavioral theory.

This theoretical framework posits that behavior is guided by intention, which in turn is shaped by attitudes towards the behavior and subjective norms. A person's attitude toward a behavior will be influenced by their beliefs about its effects, and this attitude will then affect their intention to engage in the behavior. Considering this supposition, changing an individual's beliefs, attitudes, and intentions can lead to a change in their behavior.

University life is a critical period that is characterized by major obstacles and changes, such as social transitions, academic expectations, and personal growth. According to Kessler et al. (2005), these events might cause psychological stress and mental health problems like anxiety, depression, and stress-related disorders in a lot of students. Even though these problems are common, Pakistani university students frequently show a reluctance to seek psychological treatment. University students'

psychological help-seeking behavior is said to be poor worldwide; fewer than one-third of students with common mental problems say they have sought treatment from reliable sources. Long-term impairment and poor mental health outcomes, including suicide, are linked to not seeking treatment (Gebreegziabher, Girma, & Tesfaye, 2019).

Method

Research Objective

The objectives of present study are:

1. To examine the attitudes, beliefs, perception and knowledge about psychological health among Pakistani University Students and their influence on help-seeking behavior.
2. To explore the cultural, social, and religious factors that shape help-seeking behavior for mental health issues in Pakistani University Students.

Research Questions

1. What are the perceptions and attitudes of university students towards psychological help-seeking?
2. What are the main barriers that prevent university students from seeking psychological help?
3. How do cultural and social factors influence university students' attitudes towards psychological help-seeking?

Conceptual Definitions

The variables of the study defined as follows:

Help Seeking Behavior. The act of actively seeking assistance from others is known as "help seeking" and involves reaching out to others for understanding, counsel, information, treatment, and overall support in the face of a crisis or upsetting event (Rickwood et al., 2008).

Psychological Help Seeking. According to WHO psychological help seeking is defined as any action or activity carried out by an individual who perceives herself/himself as needing personal, psychological, affective assistance or health or social services, with the purpose of meeting this need in a positive way.

Research design

The psychological help-seeking behavior was investigated in this study using a qualitative research design and Reflective Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019) as a method of data analysis. Reflexive thematic analysis was employed to analyze the data from the current study and produce the results. The six stages of reflexive thematic analysis that were used in this study are as follows:

1. Familiarizing yourself with your data
2. Generating Codes
3. Generating initial themes
4. Developing and reviewing themes
5. Defining and Naming Themes
6. Producing a report

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The current study sample was based on fourteen participants which was selected through convenient sampling technique. Convenience sampling, according to Creswell (2012), is a sampling technique in which participants are chosen by the researcher based solely on their availability and willingness to be investigated. The predetermined criteria for the current research endeavor were as follows. Firstly, the participant needed to be current university student. Second, individuals had to be between the ages of 18 and 30. This resulted from earlier studies that showed students in that age range to be particularly at risk (Macaskill, 2012).

Table 1

Participant Inclusion

	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
University Status	Currently Enrolled university students	School and College students
Age	18-30 years old	Under 18 and more than 30 years old

Participants

Fourteen participants took part in this research project. All the participant meets the inclusion criteria which was mentioned above. Participants age ranged from 22 to 27 in which (n=6) were male students and

(n=8) were female students. Two of participants are enrolled at undergraduate, eight are enrolled at graduation level and four participants are studying at Master level.

Demographic Information Sheet

Table 2

Demographic detail of Participants (N=14)

Participant	Age	Education	Gender
1	24	BS (7 th semester)	Female
2	25	BS (8 th semester)	Male
3	22	BS (4 th Semester)	Male
4	23	BS (7 th semester)	Male
5	24	BS (8 th semester)	Male
6	25	BS (6 th semester)	Male
7	26	BS (8 th semester)	Female
8	27	MS (3 rd semester)	Female
9	27	M.Phil (3 rd semester)	Female

10	26	M.Phil (2 nd semester)	Female
11	25	BS (7 th semester)	Female
12	25	BS (8 th semester)	Male
13	27	MS (4 th semester)	Female
14	26	BS (8h semester)	Female

Procedure of Data Collection

Prior to conducting interviews, informed consent was acquired from the students to confirm their willingness to take part. The research aim and purpose were presented to the participating students, along with a briefing on the confidentiality of the information they submitted. In second phase before the interviews began, participants were made aware that the sessions would be recorded and that would be last between 35 and 45 minutes. Open-ended, semi-structured interviews were conducted, and the transcripts of the verbatim were used for thematic analysis. At the end of each interview, the researcher thanked the participants.

Data Gathering Tool

The interview guide used in this study was developed with the assistance of my supervisor to ensure it aligned with the research objectives. The guide was semi-structured, allowing for flexibility in the interview process. It consisted of both open-ended and more specific questions designed to explore the participants' experiences, attitudes, and perceptions related to the research topic. Depending on the responses of the participants, probing questions were also asked. Detailed Interview guideline are attached in **Appendix C**.

Ethical Consideration

Throughout the entire research project, ethical considerations were made. This was consistent with the idea that researchers should always safeguard their subjects from injury or loss and work to maintain their dignity and psychological well-being (Willig,2013). Prior to starting the study, the researchers obtained participants' ethical approval from the RIPHAH International University Psychology department.

Ethical considerations would be made while interacting with participants and authorities. Participants granted consent for interviews to be recorded during the course of the study. The freedom to leave the study at any time was guaranteed to them. Additionally, institutional review boards had to approve ethical considerations before the research could begin.

Reflexivity

Reflexivity in this research involves the continuous self-examination of the researcher's identity, experiences, and biases, acknowledging how these may influence every stage of the qualitative study—from design to data interpretation. Drawing on personal experiences as both a researcher and university student who has faced psychological help-seeking challenges, the researcher holds a dual role: empathetic peer and objective investigator. This shared background fosters trust with participants but also necessitates heightened reflexivity to prevent personal assumptions from overshadowing participants' narratives. Regular self-reflection and peer debriefing are employed to maintain ethical rigor and minimize bias. Ultimately, this study holds personal and academic significance, and through active reflexivity, the researcher aims to authentically represent the diverse help-seeking behaviors of university students.

Results

This chapter presents an in-depth investigation of university students' psychological help-seeking behavior and highlights the thematic analysis's findings. These findings deepen the understanding of the factor that impacts the psychological help seeking behavior among university students. The full outline of major themes and sub-themes are as follows:

Table 3

Outline of major themes and sub-themes (N=14)

Major Theme	Sub-themes
Mental Health Awareness	Awareness and Knowledge Stigma and Misconception
Help Seeking	Barriers to Seeking Help Facilitators of Help-Seeking Cost and Accessibility Issues
Social and Cultural Factors	Family and Cultural Influence Societal and peer influence Gender norms
Personal Coping Strategies	Individual Coping and Resilience Seeking help from informal way
Recommendation for improvement	Enhancing Mental Health Literacy Strengthening University Support Services

1. Mental Health Awareness

Exploring university students psychological help-seeking behavior reveals several important themes, one of which is mental health awareness. There was variation in the participants'

knowledge about mental health concerns; some showed an extensive understanding of the issues and resources that were available, while others showed a limited awareness.

Table 4

Mental Health Awareness (N=14)

Sub-Themes	Codes
Awareness and Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge • Limited mental health awareness
Stigma and Misconception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stigma, misconception • Negative labels • Shame • Societal stigma • Fear of judgment

Awareness and Knowledge. The subtheme of awareness and knowledge under the main theme of mental health awareness participants demonstrated varying levels of awareness regarding mental health resources on campus and in the community. While some participants were familiar with counseling services and support groups, others were unaware of these options. According to participants when there's a lack of awareness about psychological help seeking, people may misunderstand the nature of any psychological issue. They might mistakenly believe that mental health issues are simply a matter of "being weak" or that they're not real medical conditions. The responses of participant about awareness and

knowledge about psychological help seeking are discussed below that awareness and knowledge about psychological help seeking impact their behavior and attitudes.

Stigma and misconception. This is the one of the most significant themes that a student faces when they are going to seek psychological help. Data analysis also revealed that stigma and misconception about psychological help seeking among students is one of the most important factors. The response from all participants indicates that stigma can stem from various sources, including societal attitudes, cultural

norms, and fear of judgment from peers and family members.

2. Help Seeking Behavior

Help seeking behaviour is one of the most significant themes. The theme helps seeking behavior is further divided into sub themes which are barriers to help seeking behavior, facilitator to help seeking behavior and cost and accessibility issues. Exploring help

Table 5

Help Seeking Behavior (N=14)

Sub-themes	Coding
Barriers to Seeking Help	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of ego perception • Stigma, Shame and Mistrust • privacy and confidentiality concerns
Facilitators of Help-Seeking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouragement to seek help from families • respect for privacy • awareness regarding help-seeking
Cost and Accessibility Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of professional services • High fees • long waits for appointments

Barrier in Seeking Help. This theme highlights the profound impact of barriers to seeking help, which obstruct students from accessing essential support. This theme inquires the fear of ego perception, stigma, shame and mistrust, lack of family support and privacy and confidentiality concerns are significant barrier for university student. It examines that how fear of ego perception and stigma is barrier in university student help seeking. Facing stigma or fearing of ego perception and fear of stigmatization was one of the most cited barriers for students receiving mental health services. The response of participant uncovers the barrier in psychological help seeking.

Cost and Accessibility Issues. This is another theme come under the help seeking behavior which has a significant role in university student help seeking behavior. This theme suggests that issues related to cost and accessibility include high professional fees and long waits for appointments. Based on participant responses, it appears that the majority of people are reluctant to seek help because the costs associated with mental health professionals are too high for them. Additionally, waiting long for an appointment

seeking attitudes of students indicates that they face both facilitator and barrier. Help-seeking barriers and facilitators can significantly impact an individual's willingness and ability to seek assistance when facing challenges or experiencing distress. The response from students on each theme is explained below in table 5.

negatively affects their help-seeking behavior. Students express the opinion that psychological counseling services are expensive and that only the rich and famous can afford to use them. Some students even claim that they are unable to attend the psychological counseling center because they are struggling with their finances.

Facilitator in Help Seeking. This theme comes under the help seeking behavior which identifies the strong facilitator of university student. The facilitators which help the individuals to seek help are encouragement from family and friends, respect of privacy and reassurance in help seeking. According to participant views if they have positive family and friends support they play an important role in their help seeking behavior. Another concern which was identified is respect for privacy is that maintaining confidentiality and respecting individuals' privacy when they seek assistance.

3. Social and Cultural Factors

Social and cultural factors are an extensive group of influences that shape people's experiences, attitudes, behaviors, and beliefs in relation to their social and

cultural environments. These elements greatly influence several aspects of human existence, such as health-related behaviors, help-seeking behaviors, and resource and support accessibility. Social and cultural factors might have a significant influence on university students' help-seeking behavior. Participants were asked to discuss how social and cultural variables affect their behavior while seeking

help in this part of the study. Nearly every participant stated that their social and cultural surroundings had a psychological impact on their attitude about asking for help, particularly in this environment. So, in this context different sub themes which are explained below in table 6.

Table 6
Social and Cultural Factors (N=14)

Sub themes	Codes
Family and Cultural Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive Family support • Cultural barriers • Cultural expectations • Religious practices • Communication barrier among family members
Societal and peer influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social and peer dynamics • Positive relationship with peer • Social expectations
Gender norms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Males are considered emotionally strong • Female are considered emotionally weak

Family and Cultural Factors. The subtheme of family and cultural influence under the main theme of social and cultural factors indicates the participant's response that family and culture have a greater impact on help seeking behavior among university students. This sub theme indicates that positive family support has a positive impact on help seeking behavior. The participant response indicates that if they have a supportive family they feel confident while sharing their problems with and they can go for help seeking. The cultural factor indicates the Cultural beliefs and practices related to health, illness, and help-seeking behavior vary widely across different cultural groups. These beliefs may influence individuals' explanations for mental health symptoms, preferred coping strategies, and attitudes toward seeking professional help.

Societal and Peer Influence. This theme indicates that societal and peer influence play significant roles in shaping the help-seeking behavior of university students. This sub-theme focuses on the influence of peer support networks, friendship circles, and other social connections on students' help-seeking behavior.

It explores how the presence of supportive peers can encourage students to seek help, whereas a lack of supportive social networks may deter them from seeking assistance. This theme also examines the student response that how societal expectation affect their help seeking decision.

Gender Norms. Another theme which influences help seeking behavior among university students is gender norms. This theme indicates the thoughtful consideration of the participant findings that it is common for men to be expected to be emotionally strong and independent, while women are encouraged to be more nurturing and expressive. When it comes to asking for help, these standards can put up hurdles for both genders. Men may feel that they must solve issues on their own in order to be considered masculine, while women may worry about being seen as weak or overly dependent.

4. Personal Coping Strategies

There are many coping strategies to deal with any problem but in university students data indicates that they have mainly focus on personal coping strategies to incase of help seeking. Personal coping strategies

encompass a wide range of approaches, including verbalizing concerns, self-reliance and conditional help seeking. These strategies can emerge as themes within the data, providing insights into how students

navigate stressors and setbacks. Below table 7 shows the subthemes, codes and their detailed explanations of participant views.

Table 7
Coping Strategies

Sub-themes	Coding
Individual Coping and Resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coping through verbal communication • Self-reliance • Conditional help seeking
Seeking help from informal way	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbalizing concerns through informal help • Comfort in sharing with others • Personal growth in sharing with friends

Individual Coping and Resilience. Under this sub theme the student’s response towards psychological help seeking behavior are influenced by personal coping strategies that are more reliable than any psychological counseling services. The data gather regarding this sub theme indicates that student mainly focus on to cope with their psychological health related problem through verbal communication and self-reliance. The views in the sub theme self-reliance indicate that students try to solve their problem on their own rather than asking help others. They even believe that problems can only be solved and have to be solved by the people themselves. They say that problems can be solved more effectively this way. Another view of this theme coping through verbal communication indicates that problems can be solved by verbalizing their issues with other instead of taking psychological help.

Seeking help from informal way. This sub theme indicates that students have another coping strategy for their problems are seeking help from others like sharing with friends and family. According to student perceptions on this sub-theme, asking for informal

help from others is a coping mechanism that goes beyond the services provided by psychological treatment. They indicate that they would rather ask their family or close friends for help because they believe this is a more successful way to deal with problems than turning to psychological treatment services. Some of the participants felt heard and understood when they reached out to loved ones.

5. Recommendation for Improvements in mental health awareness

In this theme students emphasized the need for increased mental health awareness, which includes normalizing and de-stigmatizing the process of seeking assistance for psychological issues. This theme includes strengthening university counseling support services and raising mental health literacy. This suggests that fostering a culture in which asking for help with mental health concerns is seen as a brave and positive move rather than a sign of weakness or failure. Universities may greatly improve the academic performance and general well-being of their students by creating an atmosphere in which people feel comfortable asking for help and supported in doing so.

Table 8

Recommendation for improvement in mental health awareness

Sub themes	Codes
Enhancing Mental Health Literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proactive guidance • Promoting awareness campaign and seminars
Strengthening University Support Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help seeking services • Counseling services • Proper formation of mental health platforms

Enhancing mental health Literacy. Another crucial theme which was identified exploring psychological help seeking among university student is enhancing mental health literacy. Understanding mental health illnesses, knowing how to get treatment, and being aware of the resources that are accessible are all considered aspects of mental health literacy. Universities can equip students to identify mental health issues in themselves or their friends and can motivate them to seek appropriate support by encouraging mental health literacy.

Improving mental health literacy in the context of university students' help-seeking behavior involves providing instruction and resources that raise students' understanding and consciousness of mental health concerns. One approach that was often suggested to address the stigma associated with mental health and the lack of knowledge about mental health problems was awareness campaigns. Many students mentioned the importance of educating University students about the fact that mental health issues are not uncommon, a show of weakness, or an indication that one is broken. This contains details on common mental health conditions, warning signs and symptoms to look out for, and campus locations for private counseling services.

Strengthen University support services. An essential theme for improving help-seeking behavior among university students is the enhancement of university support services. These services include peer support groups, mental health resources, counseling services, and other ways to get help. Ensuring that these support services are easily accessible, responsive to the needs of students, and widely promoted across the campus community is essential to strengthening them. Universities can successfully remove barriers to help-seeking and give students the resources they need

to prioritize their mental health by strengthening support services.

Discussion

The reflexive thematic analysis of interviews in this study explored psychological help-seeking behavior among university students. Five major themes emerged: mental health awareness, help-seeking attitudes, social and cultural factors, personal coping strategies, and recommendations for improving awareness. Together, these themes reflect the students' perspectives on the barriers, facilitators, and influences shaping their help-seeking behavior. This discussion elaborates on these findings, linking them with existing literature while emphasizing their implications.

Mental health awareness was found to be a significant factor influencing students' willingness to seek treatment. While some participants showed strong comprehension of mental health issues, others demonstrated limited awareness. As Jorm et al. (1997) explained, mental health literacy involves the ability to recognize disorders, access information, and understand treatment options, whereas awareness represents acknowledgment of mental health as a societal issue (Araya et al., 2003). The findings confirm that limited literacy impedes timely help-seeking, consistent with Gulliver et al. (2010), who reported that students often delay treatment due to difficulty recognizing symptoms. Stigma, misconceptions, and lack of education were identified as major contributors to low awareness, aligning with the findings of Pokharel and Pokharel (2017) and Zolezzi et al. (2014).

Help-seeking attitudes were shaped by barriers and facilitators. Students identified concerns about ego, confidentiality, and privacy as major barriers, echoing earlier findings (Eisenberg et al., 2009; Mojtabai et al., 2011). Facilitators included family encouragement

and mental health education, consistent with Vidourek and Burbage (2020) and other studies highlighting the role of social support (Stunden et al., 2020). Financial constraints also emerged as an important barrier, as many students perceived psychological services as unaffordable. This finding aligns with previous research linking higher income to more positive help-seeking attitudes (Parent et al., 2018; Hammer et al., 2013; Arslantaş et al., 2011).

Social and cultural factors further influenced help-seeking behaviors. Participants described how gender roles, peer norms, and family expectations shaped attitudes toward seeking help. These findings are consistent with Wendt and Shafer (2015); Addis and Mahalik (2003), who emphasized that men are socialized to value independence and self-reliance, making them less likely to seek help. Stigma also played a powerful role, as students feared negative judgments from society, confirming earlier work by Kroska and Harkness (2008) and Sue & Sue (1999).

Personal coping strategies were another significant theme. Students often preferred informal coping such as sharing with friends or family, self-reliance, or religious practices rather than seeking professional help. This finding aligns with Allen et al. (2016), who observed that students rely heavily on individual coping before turning to formal services. Such tendencies suggest limited knowledge about available counseling resources and their potential benefits.

Finally, recommendations for improvement centered on reducing stigma, improving access, strengthening peer support, and fostering cultural sensitivity. Students highlighted the importance of awareness campaigns, seminars, and early interventions. Prior research (Heijnders & Meij, 2008; Clement et al., 2015) supports the view that campus-based awareness initiatives, using platforms such as social media, posters, and events, can enhance openness and normalize mental health discussions.

In conclusion, this study shows that psychological help-seeking among university students is shaped by a combination of awareness, attitudes, cultural norms, coping preferences, and accessibility. An integrated, campus-wide approach that prioritizes proactive counseling, awareness campaigns, and strengthened support services can create a more inclusive environment where students feel empowered to seek help without stigma or fear.

Conclusion

The exploration of psychological help-seeking behavior among university students has revealed critical insights into the factors influencing their willingness and ability to seek psychological help. This study emphasizes that stigma, ignorance, and false beliefs about mental health continue to be major obstacles. Many students choose to use informal coping techniques like confiding in friends or being self-reliant instead of seeking professional help because they feel ashamed or afraid of being judged.

In summary, the research highlights the need of tackling the cultural, societal, and individual elements that influence students' tendencies to seek help. Universities can significantly contribute to the improvement of their students' mental health prospects by creating a more open and accepting university environment.

Limitations

This study has certain limitations. Firstly, the small sample size limits the generalizability of findings to all Pakistani university students. Second, as a qualitative study, results provide in-depth insights but cannot be widely generalized; future research could include quantitative methods. Third, the conclusions may be context-specific to the studied universities and not applicable to other regions or Pakistani students abroad. Finally, the focus on university students excludes other groups, such as working professionals or adolescents, whose help-seeking behaviors may differ.

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